

FLIPPED TEACHING - AN ACTIVE INVERTED CLASS ROOM METHOD

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Abstract:

This paper pertaining to traditional learning is integrating technology into the overall course design and delivery to flip the course. Traditional lecturing in the classroom and the material is delivered out of the classroom through the use of online technology, while the traditional homework is done in class with even greater potential for student learning through the use of Active Learning or Experiential learning activities using a team approach. Technology can also be used in the classroom and assessment can be done both online and in class. Flipping experience will be easier and better understanding of classroom and what are the benefits and challenges of flipping a class. It would reduce the amount of time spent in class on lecturing without sacrificing coverage of the content. Students need opportunities for continuing discussion for peer learning and students focus more on understanding and application and greater sense of responsibility for their learning process. This is an innovative teaching method for competitive world to enable the students to be a very good personality for achieving anything in their life. This method may be implemented in the Government high and higher secondary schools for widening their subject knowledge with conceptual and constructive view.

Keywords: *New technology, blended learning and flipped learning*

INTRODUCTION

Concept of Flipped Learning

Flipped classroom is a form of blended learning in which students learn content online by watching video lectures, usually at home, and homework is done in class with teachers and students discussing and solving questions. Teacher interaction with students is more personalized guidance instead of lecturing. This is also called as backwards classroom, inverted classroom, and reverse teaching. The traditional pattern of teaching has been to assign students to read textbooks and work on problem sets outside school, while listening to lectures and taking tests in class. In flip teaching, the students first study the topic by themselves, typically using video lessons prepared by the teacher or third parties. In class students apply the knowledge by solving problems and doing practical work. The teacher tutors the students when they become stuck, rather than imparting the initial lesson in person. Complementary techniques include differentiated instruction and project-based learning. Flipped classrooms free class time for hands-on work. Students learn by doing and asking questions. Students can also help each other, a process that benefits both the advanced and less advanced learners. Flipping also changes the allocation of teacher time. Traditionally, the teacher engages with the students who ask questions but those who don't ask tend to need the most attention. Flipping allows her to target those who need the most help rather than the most confident. Flipping changes teachers from "sage on the stage" to "guide on the side", allowing them to work with individuals or groups of students throughout the session.

Mastery Flipped Learning

Traditionally, each topic in class receives a fixed amount of time for all students. Students who do not master the material get no extra time. Mastery learning upends this approach, by requiring each student to master the topic before moving to the next one. Flipped mastery learning applies the mastery concept to flipped classrooms.

According to Benjamin Bloom in 1968 Mastery learning was briefly popular in the 1920s. It has shown dramatic success. The teacher provides materials, tools and support. Students set goals and manage their time. Mastery rewards students for displaying competence. Students who initially turn in shoddy work must correct it before moving on. Before flipping, mastery learning was impractical in most schools. It was not possible to give different lectures for different groups of students. Testing was also impractical, because fast-learning students could reveal the test to those who followed.

Selecting and sorting process is to utilize Blooms taxonomy:

- a. Knowledge – restate information - Suitable for online learning
- b. Comprehension – explain concept and assessment using online technology tools.
- c. Application – apply information
- d. Analysis – analyze a situation
- e. Synthesis – integrate and diagnose
- f. Evaluation - judge -

Suitable for classroom learning and assessment

In a flipped mastery classroom, students view each lecture and work on each exercise or project when they have mastered the precursors. 2013 onwards few teachers only had blended flipping and mastery. Flipped mastery eliminates two other out-of-class routines: daily lesson planning and grading papers. The latter happens in class and in person. Replacing lectures with group and individual activities increases in-class activity. Every student has something to do throughout the class. In some classes, students choose how to demonstrate mastery - testing, writing, speaking, debating and even designing a related game. Moodle provides one way to manage the testing process. It creates a different test for each student from a pool of questions. Advocates claim that its efficiency allows most students to do a year's work in much less time. Advanced students work on independent projects while slower learners get more personalized instruction. Some students might not get through the year's material, but demonstrated competence on the parts they did complete.

Usage of Flipping Courses Include

- 1. Improved student learning (Active Learning & assignments not as dependent on instructors availability)
- 2. Reduced costs (Less time lecturing and grading; design course once and repeat)
- 3. Ability to reach more students (increase capacity)
- 4. Students have more flexibility in using their time

Flipped Pedagogical Method

The flipped classroom is a pedagogical model in which the typical lecture and homework elements of a course are reversed. Short video lectures are viewed by students at home before the class session, while in-class time is devoted to exercises, projects, or discussions. The video lecture is often seen as the key ingredient in the flipped approach, such lectures being either created by the instructor and posted online or selected from an online repository. While a pre-recorded lecture could certainly be a podcast or other audio format, the ease with which video can be accessed and viewed today has made it so ubiquitous that the flipped model has come to be identified with it. The notion of a flipped classroom draws on such concepts as active learning, student engagement, hybrid course design, and course podcasting. The value of a flipped class is in the repurposing of class time into a workshop where students can inquire about lecture content, test their skills in applying knowledge, and interact with one another in hands-on

activities. During class sessions, instructors function as coaches or advisors, encouraging students in individual inquiry and collaborative effort.

Working method

There is no single model for the flipped classroom, the term is widely used to describe almost any class structure that provides prerecorded lectures followed by in-class exercises. In one common model, students might view multiple lectures of five to seven minutes each. Online quizzes or activities can be interspersed to test what students have learned. Immediate quiz feedback and the ability to rerun lecture segments may help clarify points of confusion. Instructors might lead in-class discussions or turn the classroom into a studio where students create, collaborate, and put into practice what they learned from the lectures they view outside class. As on-site experts, instructors suggest various approaches, clarify content, and monitor progress. They might organize students into an ad hoc workgroup to solve a problem that several are struggling to understand. Because this approach represents a comprehensive change in the class dynamic, some instructors have chosen to implement only a few elements of the flipped model or to flip only a few selected class sessions during a term.

Structure of Flipped Classrooms

The structure of the course is what determines if it is a flipped classroom.

Before class: Students watch video lectures or perform other activities to expose them to content.

Tip: Breaking lectures into smaller conceptual chunks can help students manage content.

During class: Students participate in active learning activities to deepen their understanding of the content.

Tip: Brief quizzes to check for understanding helps students and professors identify misunderstandings and ensure that the student is prepared for class.

After class: Students complete homework assignments independently to practice mastery of learned concepts.

Tip: Because part of the students' homework is learning the content for the next class, assign students less traditional homework than in a normal class.

Intermittently: Students complete assessments and provide instructor feedback about course and learning activities.

Tip: Request student feedback before major assessments to address issues.

Significance of Flipped Learning

In a traditional lecture, students often try to capture what is being said at the instant the speaker says it. They cannot stop to reflect upon what is being said, and they may miss significant points because they are trying to transcribe the instructor's words. By contrast, the use of video and other prerecorded media puts lectures under the control of the students: they can watch, rewind, and fast-forward as needed. This ability may be of particular value to students with accessibility concerns, especially where captions are provided for those with hearing impairments. Lectures that can be viewed more than once may also help those for whom English is not their first language. Devoting class time to application of concepts might give instructors a better opportunity to detect errors in thinking, particularly those that

are widespread in a class. At the same time, collaborative projects can encourage social interaction among students, making it easier for them to learn from one another and for those of varying skill levels to support their peers.

As the flipped class becomes more popular, new tools may emerge to support the out-of-class portion of the curriculum. In particular, the ongoing development of powerful mobile devices will put a wider range of rich, educational resources into the hands of students, at times and places that are most convenient for them. Greater numbers of courses will likely employ elements of the flipped classroom, supplementing traditional out-of-class work with video presentations and supporting project-based and lab-style efforts during regular class times. At a certain level of adoption, colleges and universities may need to take a hard look at class spaces to ensure they support the kinds of active and collaborative work common in flipped classes.

Classroom Activities

Below are learning activities that you may use in your classroom to help students better understand the content and learn general and domain-specific skills. These activities may vary by class depending on what is most appropriate for learning during that class period.

a. Applications and Extensions

In applications, students apply what they've learned to solve problems or analyze scenarios. Applications allow students to think about concepts from various, practical points of view. For example, in a math course, ask students to apply formulas to solve problems.

In extensions, students derive theoretical extensions of the content that they've learned. These activities encourage students to apply concepts in a novel way and deepen their understanding. For example, if students are taught to solve a specific type of problem, add another component to the problem or change the problem in a manner that requires them to solve the problem in a different way.

b. Sequence of Questions

The instructor helps students break complex problems into smaller parts to solve systematically. For this strategy, it is important to: 1) pick the right problem; 2) break it down; 3) solve incrementally; 4) allow students time to think about the question; 5) don't assign too many large problems; and 6) ask students to contribute more than simple recall of information. For example, a mathematical proof may be a good problem for sequencing.

c. Experiential Learning

In experiential learning, students learn through immersive, hands-on learning experiences. Some examples of experiential learning activities are experiments, demonstrations, trips, labs, and debates. When planning these activities make sure that: 1) students are actively involved in the experience; 2) students have the opportunity to cooperate with their peers; 3) students have time to reflect on the experience; and 4) students have the skills to adequately complete the experience.

Discussion Activities

Class discussions may make course content more meaningful and relevant to students by helping them understand diverse perspectives, test assumptions, improve communication skills, and develop a better understanding of their own perspectives. To promote successful discussions, try: 1) setting clear expectations for participation and

interaction; 2) beginning with thoughtful questions, quotes, current events, or controversial statements about content; and 3) keeping the conversation from digressing.

Small Group Problem Solving

Students solve problems in small groups with the help of instructors or TAs. The instructor or TA may also probe the students to explain their answers. Throughout the class or at the end of class, the instructor may review the solutions to the problems and provide formative feedback to the students.

Forming Groups

1. Clearly define expectations of group work.
2. Structure groups based on the needs of the project.
3. Create specific roles within groups.
4. Keep groups as small as possible.
5. Group members by ability level (e.g., equivalent GPA).

Peer Feedback

The benefits of peer feedback are two-fold: the evaluated students receive feedback about their work and the evaluating students learn from reviewing another student's work. Consider using peer feedback, especially in writing intensive or open-ended-question-intensive courses.

Learning Assessment

a. Summative Assessment

Summative assessments are used to determine if students have achieved learning objectives. Summative assessments are assessments such as tests or papers given at the end of instruction on a topic to determine what the student learned. When you flip your class, your learning objectives might change. For example, a previous learning objective might have been focused on learning content whereas a new objective might focus on being able to solve problems. Just as it is important to make sure your learning activities correspond with your learning objectives, it is important to make sure your assessments correspond with your learning objectives.

b. Formative Assessment

The central purpose of formative assessment is to contribute to student learning through the provision of information about performance (Yorke, 2003; pp. 478). Unlike summative assessment, formative assessment occurs during the learning process rather than assessing the end result of the learning process. It is also important in formative assessment that students change their behavior based on feedback. Incorporating formative assessment is an important benefit of flipped classrooms because flipping the class frees up class time for interaction with the instructor and students receive more formative feedback about their performance before completing summative assessments. This sort of interaction can be easier on the professor too because feedback may be less formal and students may ask for clarifications or elaborations.

Educational implications

The flipped classroom constitutes a role change for instructors, who give up their front-of-the-class position in favor of a more collaborative and cooperative contribution to the teaching process. There is a concomitant change in the role of students, many of whom are used to being cast as passive participants in the education process, where

instruction is served to them. The flipped model puts more of the responsibility for learning on the shoulders of students while giving them greater impetus to experiment. Activities can be student-led, and communication among students can become the determining dynamic of a session devoted to learning through hands-on work. What the flip does particularly well is to bring about a distinctive shift in priorities from merely covering material to working toward mastery of it.

Conclusion

Flipping experience will be easier and better understanding of classroom and what are the benefits and challenges of flipping a class. It would reduce the amount of time spent in class on lecturing without sacrificing coverage of the content. Students need opportunities for continuing discussion for peer learning and students focus more on understanding and application and greater sense of responsibility for their learning process. This is an innovative teaching method for competitive world to enable the students to be a very good personality for achieving anything in their life. This method may be implemented in the Government high and higher secondary schools for widening their subject knowledge with conceptual and constructive view.

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